

Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship using MLR Method for Nitrobenzenes Toxicity to *tetrahymena pyriformis*

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ABSTRACT: The toxicity data of 42 nitroaromatic compounds related to 50% growth inhibitory concentration ($\log IGC_{50}^1$) were used to develop Quantitative structure toxicity relationship to *tetrahymena pyriformis*. The multiple linear regression method was applied to select the descriptors. The six parametric model were found to be the best which gives a variance of more than 92% ($R^2=0.9248$). Our results have shown that six parametric model containing second order connectivity, a physicochemical parameter, distance based Balaban and Balaban type of indices along with indicator parameter play a dominating role in modeling toxicity ($\log IGC_{50}^1$). The predictive powers of the models were also discussed by using the method of cross-validation. Our results are comparatively better than the result obtained by E.Estrada and and E.Uriarte.

Keywords: *tetrahymena pyriformis*, Biological activity, indicator parameter, physicochemical parameters, topological parameters, $\log IGC_{50}^1$ growth inhibitory concentration, which causes the death of 50% (one half) of a group of test animals

INTRODUCTION

The nitro substituted aromatic compounds (NAC's) released in the Biosphere almost exclusively from anthropogenic sources .some compounds are produced by incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, others are used as synthetic intermediates, dyes, pesticides and explosives [1].

The presence of these aromatic xenobiotics in the environment may create serious public health and environmental problems. Some of these compounds have mutagenic and carcinogenic activity and may bioaccumulation in the food chain [2]. Many nitro aromatics have also been toxic to microorganisms [3]. The nature and the degree of aromatic substitution were concluded to have profound effect on the toxicity of NAC's compounds [4].

There are several experimental methods available for screening the toxicity level of such compounds (eg in vivo and vitro assay tests) and these have been carried out using receptors and other biological materials of human , rats and calf original least [5]. However this can be costly time

consuming and could potentially produced toxic side effects from the experimental method used today. This means that the development of computational method as an alternative tool for predicting properties of chemicals have been a subject of intensive study.

Among the computational method the, QSAR relationships have found diverse application for predicting the compound properties, including biological activity prediction [6-10].

Acute toxicity is studies on various species unicellular organisms (eg algae), invertebrates (eg *Daphnia Magma*) and vertebrates (eg fish). We have selected the toxicity of nitro aromatic compounds to *tetrahymena pyriformis* describing QSAR modeling.

The studies on QSAR for relating the chemical or biological activity of drugs or aromatic compounds has led to proliferation of methods and indices [11-13]. Such methods include various forms of univariate or multivariate regressions .At a fundamental level ,indices include various forms of pure graph invariants commonly called topological indices. Such as Wiener (W), Randic ($^m\chi$), Kier and Hall ($^m\chi^v$) indices. There have been a large number of other less fundamental indices,

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which have attempted to capture the essence of molecular shape, reactivity and polarity. Such indices are successfully used in modeling of biological activity of organic compounds toxic to the external environment.

The primary aim of present investigation is that we have chosen the diverse set of 42 nitroaromatic compounds and modeling their GIC^{1}_{50} using a larger set of physicochemical parameters, distance based topological indices. The results as discussed below shows that excellent mode is obtained when these indices are coupled with indicator parameters.

Many works have been performed using T. pyriformis to develop linear models in recent years [14-23] additionally some non-linear method also applied [24-26] to predict aquatic toxicity in T. pyriformis.

A series of papers have been published using physicochemical parameters and topological descriptors simultaneously for successful modeling of biological activities for various drug molecules [27-31].

EXPERIMENTAL

50% Growth Inhibitory Concentration ($\log IGC^{1}_{50}$) Activity

The toxicity parameter studied here is the 50% growth inhibitory concentration of nitro benzenes to Tetrahymena Pyriformis stain GL-C($\log IGC^{1}_{50}$) as reported earlier is used.

Molecular Descriptors Used

Several physicochemical parameters for the 42 nitro aromatic compounds (Table 1) were calculated using ACD Lab software chem sketch [32]. Topological indices for the 42 nitro benzenes have been calculated using Dragon software. They are Wiener index, Balaban and Balaban type of index, Randic, Kier and hall connectivity indices. They are reported in table 2 and table 3 respectively. All the topological indices were calculated from the hydrogen suppressed graphs. These graphs were obtained after deleting all the carbon-hydrogen as well as heteroatoms-hydrogen bonds from the molecular structures of the compound used. The structure optimization for using Dragon software was made by ACD Lab's software.

Table 1
Structural Details and their $\log IGC^{1}_{50}$ Values of the Compounds Used in the Present Study

Compd No.	Compounds name	$\log IGC^{1}_{50}$	IPI
1	2,6-Dimethylnitrobenzene	0.300	0
2	2,3-Dimethylnitrobenzene	0.560	0
3	2-methyl-3-chloronitrobenzene	0.680	1
4	2-Methylnitrobenzene	0.052	0
5	2-Chloronitrobenzene	0.680	1
6	2-methyl-5-chloronitrobenzene	0.820	1
7	2,4,5-Trichloronitrobenzene	1.530	1
8	2,5-Dichloronitrobenzene	1.130	1
9	6-Chloro-1,3-dinitrobenzene	1.980	1
10	Nitrobenzene	0.140	0
11	3-Methylnitrobenzene	0.054	0
12	1,3-Dinitrobenzene	0.890	0
13	3,4-Dichloronitrobenzene	1.160	1
14	4-Methylnitrobenzene	0.170	0
15	1,4-Dinitrobenzene	1.300	0
16	4-Chloronitrobenzene	0.430	1
17	2,3,5,6-Tetrachloronitrobenzene	1.820	1
18	6-Methyl-1,3-dinitrobenzene	0.870	0
19	3-Chloronitrobenzene	0.730	1
20	1,2-Dinitrobenzene	1.250	0
21	2-Bromonitrobenzene	0.750	1
22	6-Bromo-1,3-dinitrobenzene	2.310	1
23	3-Bromonitrobenzene	1.030	1
24	4-Bromonitrobenzene	0.380	1
25	2,4,6-Trimethylnitrobenzene	0.860	0
26	5-Methyl-1,2-dinitrobenzene	1.520	0
27	2,4-dichloronitrobenzene	0.990	1
28	3,5-dichloronitrobenzene	1.130	1
29	6-Iodo-1,3-dinitrobenzene	2.120	1
30	2,3,4,5-Tetrachloronitrobenzene	1.780	1
31	2,3-Dichloronitrobenzene	1.070	1
32	2,5,-Dibromonitrobenzene	1.370	1
33	1,2-Dichloro-4,5-dinitrobenzene	2.210	1
34	3-Methyl-4-bromonitrobenzene	1.160	1
35	2,3,4-Trichloronitrobenzene	1.510	1
36	2,4,6-Trichloronitrobenzene	1.430	1
37	4,6-Dichloro-1,2-dinitrobenzene	2.420	1
38	3,5-Dinitrobenzyl alcohol	0.530	0
39	3,4-Dinitrobenzyl alcohol	1.090	0
40	2,4,6-Trichloro-1,3-dinitrobenzene	2.190	1
41	2,3,5,6-Tetrachloro-1,4-dinitrobenzene	2.740	1
42	2,5,6-Trichloro-1,3-dinitrobenzene	2.590	1

IPI=1 if halogens present in compounds, otherwise zero.

Table 2
Calculated Physicochemical Parameters for Compounds (Table 1) used in Present Study

<i>Compd. No.</i>	<i>MW</i>	<i>IR</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>POL</i>
1	151.163	1.547	1.129	16.820
2	151.163	1.547	1.129	16.800
3	171.581	1.570	1.324	16.850
4	137.136	1.553	1.166	14.910
5	157.554	1.580	1.391	14.940
6	171.581	1.570	1.324	16.850
7	226.445	1.609	1.651	18.820
8	192.000	1.595	1.533	16.880
9	202.552	1.625	1.618	17.530
10	123.109	1.561	1.215	13.000
11	137.136	1.553	1.166	14.910
12	168.107	1.612	1.486	15.590
13	192.000	1.595	1.533	16.880
14	137.136	1.553	1.166	14.910
15	168.107	1.612	1.486	15.590
16	157.554	1.580	1.391	14.940
17	260.890	1.620	1.750	20.760
18	182.134	1.598	1.407	17.500
19	157.554	1.580	1.391	14.940
20	168.107	1.612	1.486	15.590
21	202.005	1.605	1.719	16.050
22	247.003	1.647	1.910	18.640
23	202.005	1.605	1.719	16.050
24	202.005	1.605	1.719	16.050
25	165.189	1.542	1.100	18.740
26	182.134	1.598	1.407	17.500
27	192.000	1.595	1.533	16.880
28	192.000	1.595	1.533	16.880
29	294.003	1.699	2.174	20.710
30	260.890	1.620	1.750	20.760
31	192.000	1.595	1.533	16.880
32	280.902	1.640	2.101	19.090
33	236.997	1.636	1.729	19.470
34	216.032	1.592	1.615	17.960
35	226.445	1.609	1.651	18.820
36	226.445	1.609	1.651	18.820
37	236.997	1.636	1.729	19.470
38	198.133	1.641	1.560	18.150
39	198.133	1.641	1.560	18.150
40	271.442	1.645	1.822	21.410
41	305.887	1.653	1.900	23.350
42	271.442	1.645	1.822	21.410

MW=Molecular weight

IR=Refractive index

D=Density

POL=Polarizability

Table 3
Values of Various Topological Parameters for Compounds (Table 1) used in Present Study

Compd. No.	${}^2\chi$	${}^0\chi^V$	${}^2\chi^V$	W	J	JhetZ	Jhetm	Jhetv	Jhete
1	4.707	6.496	2.498	144	2.551	3.656	3.656	2.805	3.650
2	4.675	6.496	2.476	146	2.509	3.598	3.598	2.775	3.592
3	4.675	6.630	2.548	146	2.509	3.788	3.792	2.775	3.649
4	4.170	5.573	2.044	114	2.396	3.522	3.522	2.609	3.515
5	4.170	5.707	2.116	114	2.396	3.750	3.755	2.609	3.583
6	4.803	6.630	2.624	148	2.471	3.730	3.734	2.744	3.599
7	5.311	7.820	3.196	187	2.551	4.127	4.14	2.882	3.750
8	4.803	6.764	2.696	148	2.471	3.937	3.946	2.744	3.658
9	5.702	6.893	2.557	240	2.526	3.902	3.905	2.585	3.790
10	3.642	4.650	1.593	88	2.228	3.391	3.391	2.405	3.383
11	4.276	5.573	2.096	117	2.32	3.416	3.416	2.554	3.409
12	5.175	5.837	2.034	197	2.402	3.648	3.648	2.413	3.638
13	4.772	6.764	2.670	152	2.396	3.810	3.819	2.690	3.549
14	4.264	5.573	2.093	120	2.26	3.332	3.332	2.510	3.326
15	5.163	5.837	2.031	206	2.295	3.484	3.484	2.348	3.475
16	4.264	5.707	2.170	120	2.260	3.520	3.524	2.510	3.383
17	5.730	8.877	3.644	222	2.756	4.531	4.55	3.113	4.021
18	5.702	6.759	2.485	240	2.526	3.754	3.754	2.585	3.745
19	4.276	5.707	2.173	117	2.32	3.620	3.625	2.554	3.471
20	5.100	5.837	2.003	188	2.541	3.860	3.860	2.492	3.848
21	4.170	6.537	2.563	114	2.396	3.824	3.833	2.662	3.562
22	5.702	7.723	3.004	240	2.526	3.948	3.953	2.616	3.776
23	4.276	6.537	2.653	117	2.320	3.686	3.693	2.603	3.452
24	4.264	6.537	2.649	120	2.260	3.579	3.585	2.555	3.365
25	5.353	7.418	3.004	184	2.602	3.669	3.669	2.921	3.664
26	5.734	6.759	2.506	234	2.605	3.872	3.871	2.629	3.861
27	4.803	6.764	2.696	150	2.437	3.882	3.891	2.720	3.609
28	4.922	6.764	2.758	150	2.427	3.863	3.872	2.713	3.595
29	5.702	8.295	3.312	240	2.526	3.964	3.968	2.633	3.747
30	5.698	8.877	3.618	226	2.701	4.434	4.452	3.073	3.943
31	4.675	6.764	2.615	146	2.509	4.008	4.018	2.775	3.711
32	4.803	8.424	3.623	148	2.471	4.068	4.084	2.839	3.622
33	6.242	7.950	3.084	283	2.698	4.225	4.232	2.783	4.017
34	4.772	7.460	3.045	152	2.396	3.670	3.676	2.734	3.478
35	5.181	7.820	3.115	185	2.584	4.190	4.204	2.910	3.795
36	5.353	7.820	3.226	184	2.602	4.219	4.233	2.921	3.821
37	6.283	7.950	3.113	278	2.752	4.317	4.324	2.819	4.096
38	5.990	6.914	2.530	296	2.564	3.729	3.729	2.573	3.720
39	5.903	6.914	2.495	293	2.605	3.790	3.789	2.594	3.781
40	6.692	9.006	3.558	332	2.84	4.516	4.527	2.974	4.202
41	7.079	10.063	3.979	390	2.944	4.736	4.75	3.135	4.334
42	6.660	9.006	3.531	332	2.838	4.512	4.523	2.973	4.199

${}^2\chi$ = Randic connectivity index

${}^0\chi^V$ & ${}^2\chi^V$ = kier and Hall valence connectivity indices

W = Wiener index

J = Balaban index

Jhet Z, Jhetm, Jhetv, Jhete = Balaban type indices

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was made using maximum R^2 method following stepwise regression analysis. The NCSS software was used for making regression analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In modeling IGC^{-1}_{50} of the 42 nitroaromatic compounds and to arrive at most significant model. We have chosen stepwise regression analysis and used maximum R^2 method. Stepwise regression attempted by us indicated that six parametric regression give excellent statistics in modeling. For the relative comparison of results, we have

attempted mono to six parametric regression using the following combinations.

The correlation matrix showing intercorrelation among physicochemical and the topological indices is demonstrated in table 4. A perusal of this table shows that JhetZ, Jhete, Jhetm and $^2\chi$ are the best parameters for modeling the toxicity. However the topological when combined with physicochemical parameters give better results in multiparametric correlation. Therefore in multiparametric correlation topological as well as physicochemical parameters have been taken together. These correlation are reported in table 5.

Table 4
Correlation Matrix Showing Correlation among Various Descriptors and also with $logIGC^{-1}_{50}$

	$log IGC^{-1}_{50}$	MW	IR	D	POL	W	J
$logIGC^{-1}_{50}$	1						
MW	0.8575	1					
IR	0.7898	0.8466	1				
D	0.7601	0.9184	0.9158	1			
POL	0.8361	0.9062	0.6830	0.6775	1		
W	0.7850	0.6782	0.7243	0.5103	0.8092	1	
J	0.7725	0.7041	0.5235	0.4323	0.8948	0.8443	1
JhetZ	0.8539	0.8616	0.6472	0.6816	0.8885	0.7059	0.8868
Jhetm	0.8517	0.8624	0.6455	0.6834	0.8870	0.6999	0.8828
Jhetv	0.5504	0.6603	0.2228	0.3587	0.8102	0.4272	0.7872
Jhete	0.8442	0.7284	0.6197	0.5133	0.8576	0.8730	0.9731
$^2\chi$	0.8369	0.7223	0.7071	0.5286	0.8676	0.9800	0.8922
$^0\chi^v$	0.8297	0.9368	0.6659	0.7270	0.9847	0.7261	0.8486
$^2\chi^v$	0.7639	0.9215	0.5960	0.7227	0.9424	0.5933	0.7640
IP_1	0.5006	0.5988	0.4035	0.6360	0.4027	0.0586	0.2102

JhetZ	Jhetm	Jhetv	Jhete	$^2\chi$	$^0\chi^v$	$^2\chi^v$	IP_1
1							
0.9999	1						
0.8266	0.8284	1					
0.9121	0.9078	0.6924	1				
0.7709	0.7654	0.5279	0.9087	1			
0.9084	0.9084	0.8473	0.8159	0.7943	1		
0.8702	0.8719	0.8729	0.7164	0.6803	0.9819	1	
0.5518	0.5574	0.4707	0.2551	0.1301	0.5058	0.5833	1

Table 5
Regression Parameters and Quality of Correlation for the Compounds used in Present Study

Model No.	Parameters Used	$A_i = (I-6)$	B	Se	R^2	R^2A	F-ratio	$Q=R/Se$
1	JhetZ	1.8083 (± 0.1743)	-5.837	0.376	0.729	0.7224	107.629	2.2707
2	MW	0.013 (± 0.001)	-1.488	0.372	0.735	0.729	111.197	2.305
3	$^2\chi$ IP1	(0.7047 \pm 0.0549) (0.5960 \pm 0.0915)	-2.8316	0.2771	0.8566	0.8492	116.454	3.3400
4	Jhete D	(1.8489 \pm 0.2111) (1.2324 \pm 0.1955)	-7.5630	0.2760	0.8577	0.8504	117.574	3.3555
5	J Jhete POL	(-7.9743 \pm 1.0959) (5.8381 \pm 0.6743) 0.2757 \pm 0.0376)	-5.2575	0.2346	0.8999	0.8920	113.819	4.0436
6	J JhetZ Jhetm $^0\chi^v$	(-6.3379 \pm 0.9254) (161.7384 \pm 20.0332) (-156.4822 \pm 19.5249) (0.4479 \pm 0.0821)	-5.5447	0.2289	0.9071	0.8971	90.343	4.1608
7	Jhetv Jhete $^2\chi^v$ IP1 IR	(-4.1800 \pm 0.9210) (2.9431 \pm 0.3761) (1.3592 \pm 0.3024) (0.4297 \pm 0.1005) (-6.4260 \pm 3.2737)	7.9383	0.2208	0.9159	0.9042	78.426	4.3343
8	W $^0\chi$ MW $^0\chi^v$ IP1 IR	(-0.0178 \pm 0.0044) (1.8508 \pm 0.3107) (0.0584 \pm 0.0121) (2.0354 \pm 0.4175) (0.3872 \pm 0.1082) (-30.9937 \pm 7.8082)	39.7238	0.2132	0.9238	0.9107	70.692	4.5081
9	W J Jhete $^2\chi$ IP1 POL	(-0.0062 \pm 0.0027) (-6.8732 \pm 1.2997) (4.8499 \pm 0.8834) (0.8565 \pm 0.2883) (0.1964 \pm 0.1138) (0.1696 \pm 0.0550)	-5.8565	0.2118	0.9248	0.9119	71.698	4.5404

Mono-parametric Models

Stepwise regression resulted into various mono-parametric correlations. Two mono-parametric models were obtained showing better statistics.

$$\log \text{IGC}^{-1}_{50} = -5.837 + 1.8083(\pm 0.1743)\text{JhetZ}$$

n = 42, Se = 0.3760, $R^2 = 0.7291$, $R^2_A = 0.7224$,
F-ratio = 107.629, Q = 2.2707, PRESS/
SSY = 0.3714, $R^2\text{Cv} = 0.6286$ (1)

$$\log \text{IGC}^{-1}_{50} = -1.488 + 0.013(\pm 0.001)\text{MW}$$

n = 42, Se = 0.3720, $R^2 = 0.7354$, $R^2_A = 0.7290$,
F-ratio = 111.197, Q = 2.305,
PRESS/SSY = 0.3597, $R^2\text{Cv} = 0.6403$ (2)

Bi-parametric Models

The R^2 in bi-parametric correlation varies from 0.74 to 0.85. The best bi-parametric model in case of topological indices comes out to be 0.8566 with $^2\chi$ and indicator parameter IP_1 indicating the halogen atom. The model is as below:

$$\log \text{IGC}^{-1}_{50} = -2.8316 + 0.7047(\pm 0.0549)^2\chi$$

$$+ 0.5960(\pm 0.0915)\text{IP1}$$

n = 42, Se = 0.2771, $R^2 = 0.8566$, $R^2_A = 0.8492$,
F-ratio = 116.454, Q = 3.3400, PRESS/
SSY = 0.1674, $R^2\text{Cv} = 0.8326$ (3)

However when Jhete and D are taken together then R^2 comes out to be 0.8577. This clearly shows that in bi-parametric modeling this best model is a mixed model containing topological as well as physicochemical parameter. The model is as below:

$$\log \text{IGC}^{-1}_{50} = -7.5630 + 1.8489(\pm 0.2111)\text{Jhete} +$$

$$1.2324(\pm 0.1955)\text{D}$$

n = 42, Se = 0.2760, $R^2 = 0.8577$, $R^2_A = 0.8504$,
F-ratio = 117.574, Q = 3.3555, PRESS/
SSY = 0.1658, $R^2\text{Cv} = 0.8342$ (4)

Tri-parametric Model

The best tri-parametric model in case of topological indices contains J, JhetZ and $^2\chi$. In this case R^2 comes out to be 0.8631. But better tri-parametric

model is obtained when physicochemical parameter also included in MLR and the model containing J, Jhete and POL having $R^2 = 0.8999$ comes out to be the best among all the three parametric model. The model is as below:

$$\log IGC^{-1}_{50} = -5.2575 - 7.9743(\pm 1.0959)J + 5.8381(\pm 0.6743)Jhete + 0.2757(\pm 0.0376)POL \quad (5)$$

$n = 42$, $Se = 0.2346$, $R^2 = 0.8999$, $R^2_A = 0.8920$, $F\text{-ratio} = 113.819$, $Q = 4.0436$, $PRESS/SSY = 0.1112$, $R^2Cv = 0.8888$

Four-parametric Model

However in four-parametric modeling and Five-parametric modeling only topological indices have been found to be effective. The best four-parametric model containing J, JhetZ, Jhetm and ${}^0\chi$ with $R^2 = 0.9071$.

$$\log IGC^{-1}_{50} = -5.5447 - 6.3379(\pm 0.9254)J + 161.7384(\pm 20.0332)JhetZ - 156.4822(\pm 19.5249)Jhetm + 0.4479(\pm 0.0821){}^0\chi^V \quad (6)$$

$n = 42$, $Se = 0.2289$, $R^2 = 0.9071$, $R^2_A = 0.8971$, $F\text{-ratio} = 90.343$, $Q = 4.1608$, $PRESS/SSY = 0.1023$, $R^2Cv = 0.8977$

Five-parametric Model

However in case of five parametric modeling a model containing Jhetv, Jhete, ${}^2\chi^V$, IR and IP_1 comes out to be the best. The R^2 values for this model is 0.9159. The model is as below:

$$\log IGC^{-1}_{50} = 7.9383 - 4.1800(\pm 0.9210)Jhetv + 2.9431(\pm 0.3761)Jhete + 1.3592(\pm 0.3024){}^2\chi^V - 6.4260(\pm 3.2737)IR + 0.4297(\pm 0.1005)IP_1 \quad (7)$$

$n = 42$, $Se = 0.2208$, $R^2 = 0.9159$, $R^2_A = 0.9042$, $F\text{-ratio} = 78.426$, $Q = 4.3343$, $PRESS/SSY = 0.0918$, $R^2Cv = 0.9082$

Six-parametric Models

However, out of three six-parametric models. Model with W, J, Jhete, ${}^2\chi$, POL, IP_1 comes out to be the best since it gives a highest R^2 and Q value. A similar potential has been found in case of model containing W, ${}^0\chi$, MW, ${}^2\chi^V$, IR and IP_1 . The R^2 comes out to be 0.9238. Using model 8 and 9 (table 5) the toxicity values have been evaluated and reported in table 6 respectively. However, the correlation potential for these model have obtained by plotting observed versus estimated toxicity values and they are demonstrated in Fig. 1 & the Fig. 2 and predictive power of the Fig. 1 & the Fig. 2 comes out to be 0.9238 and 0.9248 suggesting that this model is the best among the three six-parametric

models. The model-8 & 9 explains more than 92% variance of the data.

Figure 1: Correlation between Observed and Estimated log IGC^{-1}_{50} using Model no. 8

Figure 2: Correlation between Observed and Estimated log IGC^{-1}_{50} using Model no. 9

$$\log IGC^{-1}_{50} = 39.7238 - 0.0178(\pm 0.0044)W + 1.8508(\pm 0.3107){}^0\chi + 0.0584(\pm 0.0121)MW + 2.0354(\pm 0.4175){}^0\chi^V - 30.9937(\pm 7.8082)IR + 0.3872(\pm 0.1082)IP_1 \quad (8)$$

$n = 42$, $Se = 0.2132$, $R^2 = 0.9238$, $R^2_A = 0.9107$, $F\text{-ratio} = 70.692$, $Q = 4.5081$, $PRESS/SSY = 0.0825$, $R^2Cv = 0.9175$

$$\log IGC^{-1}_{50} = -5.8565 - 0.0062(\pm 0.0027)W - 6.8732(\pm 1.2997)J + 4.8499(\pm 0.8834)Jhete + 0.8565(\pm 0.2883){}^2\chi + (0.1696 \pm 0.0550)POL + 0.1964 \pm 0.1138)IP_1 \quad (9)$$

$n = 42$, $Se = 0.2118$, $R^2 = 0.9248$, $R^2_A = 0.9119$, $F\text{-ratio} = 71.698$, $Q = 4.5404$, $PRESS/SSY = 0.0813$, $R^2Cv = 0.9187$

On the basis of R^2 and Q value[33] it is evident that model containing W, J, Jhete, ${}^2\chi$, POL, IP_1 is the best model for modeling $\log IGC^{-1}_{50}$ activity of the nitro compounds in the present case.

Table 6
Observed v/s Estimated $\log IGC_{50}^{-1}$ and their
Residue for Model no 8 & 9 (Table 5)

Compd. No.	Observed $\log IGC_{50}^{-1}$	Model-8 Estimated $\log IGC_{50}^{-1}$	Residual	Model-9 Estimated $\log IGC_{50}^{-1}$	Residual
1	0.300	0.423	-0.123	0.303	-0.003
2	0.560	0.387	0.173	0.267	0.293
3	0.680	0.981	-0.301	0.749	-0.069
4	0.052	0.218	-0.166	0.116	-0.064
5	0.680	0.688	-0.008	0.647	0.033
6	0.820	0.946	-0.126	0.865	-0.045
7	1.530	1.435	0.095	1.574	-0.044
8	1.130	1.090	0.040	1.156	-0.026
9	1.980	1.796	0.184	1.728	0.252
10	0.140	-0.118	0.258	0.016	0.120
11	0.054	0.165	-0.111	0.196	-0.142
12	0.890	1.105	-0.215	1.133	-0.243
13	1.160	1.019	0.141	1.091	0.069
14	0.170	0.112	0.058	0.177	-0.007
15	1.300	0.945	0.355	1.011	0.289
16	0.430	0.581	-0.151	0.655	-0.225
17	1.820	1.941	-0.121	1.950	-0.130
18	0.870	1.327	-0.457	1.308	-0.438
19	0.730	0.635	0.095	0.699	0.031
20	1.250	1.265	-0.015	1.187	0.063
21	0.750	0.819	-0.069	0.734	0.016
22	2.310	2.020	0.290	1.848	0.462
23	1.030	0.766	0.264	0.795	0.235
24	0.380	0.712	-0.332	0.756	-0.376
25	0.860	0.419	0.441	0.651	0.209
26	1.520	1.433	0.087	1.392	0.128
27	0.990	1.055	-0.065	1.139	-0.149
28	1.130	1.055	0.075	1.242	-0.112
29	2.120	1.989	0.131	2.058	0.062
30	1.780	1.870	-0.090	1.898	-0.118
31	1.070	1.126	-0.056	1.054	0.016
32	1.370	1.507	-0.137	1.356	0.014
33	2.210	2.161	0.049	2.171	0.039
34	1.160	1.099	0.061	0.93	0.230
35	1.510	1.470	0.040	1.467	0.043
36	1.430	1.488	-0.058	1.623	-0.193
37	2.420	2.250	0.170	2.249	0.171
38	0.530	0.925	-0.395	0.935	-0.400
39	1.090	0.979	0.111	0.893	0.197
40	2.190	2.484	-0.294	2.503	-0.313
41	2.740	2.674	0.066	2.729	0.010
42	2.590	2.484	0.106	2.475	0.115

CONCLUSION

1. Topological as well as physicochemical parameter are capable of modeling the toxicity of nitro benzenes.
2. The negative coefficient of Wiener index suggests that the compound having higher Wiener index will show less toxicity.
3. Balaban index has a negative coefficient in model-9 (Table-5) suggesting that presence of cyclisation has a dominant role in toxicity.
4. Compounds with more polarisibility will show more toxicity.
5. Presence of halogen is also responsible for the toxic behavior of compounds.
6. More branching will enhance the toxicity of the compounds.

Our results ($R^2=0.9248$) are comparatively better than the results ($R^2=0.9103$) obtained by E.Estrada and and E.Uriarte.

Further confirmation in favour of six parametric model is obtained by calculating the cross-validated parameters for the given models. PRESS (predicted residual sum of squares) appears to be the most important cross validation parameter accounting for a good estimate of the real predictive error of the models. Its value less than SSY (sum of squares of the response value) indicate that the model predict better than the chance and can be considered statistically significant. In our case PRESS/SSY for all the models have been more than zero, which shows that these models are free from the defect of chance and also R^2Cv is highest for the six parametric model suggesting that this model is most appropriate for modeling $\log IGC_{50}^{-1}$ value of compounds under investigation.

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